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TOXIC FEMINISM

What Feminists are afraid of?

TRUTH IS OUT HERE

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Summary: TOXIC FEMINISM covers a broad range of research on radical feminists and hatred towards men. Feminists demand equality without any responsibilities, they want a man to blame for their mistakes, their daily abuse and harassment by women against her male partner by using “women centric” laws in India and LEGAL TERRORISM to control men and dominate them. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. It is an effort to highlight the plight of men who are neglected by international organizations as well as government bodies within India and suffer in silence.

The exact numbers of such cases are difficult to assess as majority cases go unreported. It is even tougher to figure out with exactitude how many men are suffering because of “LEGAL TERRORISM”

Key Findings: Majority men feel shy to come forward to report abuse, harassment, misuse of law and so most men suffer in silence and die young. There are no support groups to help men. None of the study reports or details highlighting atrocities on men are acknowledged by any institute, government body, and the mainstream media is reluctant to publish abuse on men or health issues concerning men in particular.

Methodology: Information for this report is sourced from various secondary sources, medical journals and various news publications, testimonies, survey statistics etc.

Introduction: Analysis report on Study on TOXIC FEMINISM address following questions: What’s is Toxic or Radical Feminism? What are their goal? How to control Radical Feminism and what they are afraid off. Most of the literature collected by MyNation demonstrates that there is a dearth of research of effects of Toxic Feminism

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on men's mental health or overall health when someone is reported to be depressed due to marital distress or stressful relationship. There is no government body or agency for men in distress to consult with, no funding earmarked to encourage any organization (governmental or non-governmental) to work for men's health issues or address their socio-economic problems or to support men in distress. Because most of the Organizations or Government agencies fund only for women not for men. Every Government want to empower Women branding all women as Victims even they are villains which encourage Radical feminists control men and so to dominate. This study article / report is based on review of literature obtained from legal journals, medical journals and reference from other study reports.

Men are not against women, not because they have mother, sisters and daughters but because there are few women who really suffer in the hands of other women. Even though they have father and brothers, most women do not think twice on calling men as pig /dog and rapists all under the influence of toxic feminism.

Traits of Toxic Feminism

1. It feeds off our fear and it travels fast.

Humans are hardwired to remember negative information over positive, it's how we learn. Feminists the Peddlers of disinformation know this and play on deep emotions, which make us far more likely to share it on social media – and so it spreads up to six times faster than factual news!

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2. It thrives on social media and reaches billions.

The more time we spend on social media, the more money those companies make. They know that extreme and shocking content hooks our attention, so they program their sites to promote it. And it reaches billions. The biggest newspapers sell a few million copies, while news on Facebook reaches over a BILLION per day.

3. It is being weaponized against us.

Feminists in Western world along with some Henpecked Politicians are weaponizing feminism as the newest move in the playbook for age-old divide and rule politics with gender. Same was done in India with Religion too. But it's USA that leads the pack -- their huge 'troll farms' employ legions of people to set up millions of fake accounts to spread feminism. And its propaganda outlet is one of YouTube's most-viewed news channels with an estimated 2 billion views!

4. It is killing people and poisoning democracy.

Feminism is driving vigilante violence in India, in some countries in Asia and Arab world. It is also poisoning our politics. Fake feminism is destroying trust in mainstream media, our democratic institutions, and political leaders which is creating the perfect breeding ground for anti-establishment strongmen to rise to power and make money. Because of feminism, social media is now a threat to democracy.

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5. No one is immune.

People across the political spectrum are being micro-targeted as part of a strategy to polarize and erode our societies. In the US and EU troll army created a fake page for fake feminism activists that drew more followers than the equal rights to women movement pages!. We think we'd never fall for this stuff, but studies show that even the most educated among us tend to believe fake news, and people over 65 are even more likely to spread it.

How to Stop Toxic Feminism?

As we celebrate the 20th anniversary of UN Security Council resolution 1325, we must also recognize that trends in the digital sphere have also undermined the very goals the men, Peace and Security (MPS) agenda has sought to realize. This absence of security online hinders men's participation in the public sphere, governance and leadership roles, especially in the context of conflict prevention and in promoting social cohesion. Should this deficiency in men's engagement online in the region continue, the status quo is sure to be preserved, maintaining influence in the hands of the very powerful few, Like WCD/NCW(India) UN Women and stalling the transformative change that the MPS framework envisages. Thus, men's digital engagement and use of technologies are at a critical juncture with regards to the achievement of the MPS agenda. The following recommendations are targeted towards governments, development organizations and researchers in South and South-East Asia:

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1. Create a Ministry in each country or build the capacity of men in South and South-East Asia to identify, report and block hateful content. Also work on social media literacy and countering disinformation as the region witnesses increased volumes of misandry and hate speech targeting men online. It is crucial that men users of social media are aware of how to protect themselves. Likewise, misandrist tweets and Facebook posts especially in South Asia are often based on news stories that are fake or taken out of context. This suggests that increased levels of social media literacy among both men and women would limit the efficacy of such posts in spreading their hateful agendas.
2. Pass legislation that criminalizes cyber harassment and cyber stalking. Although States often have existing laws that prohibit stalking or harassment, these laws are sometimes inadequate to criminalize harms that happen online. Thus, specific laws to address cyber harassment and stalking can close this gap.
3. Monitor and remove misandrist content on social media platforms Social media companies have increasingly sought to regulate what content is publishable on their platforms, banning everything from election misinformation to photos depicting violence. However, no ban against misandry, particularly violent misandry has yet been introduced, which affects the safety and free speech of men users.
4. Produce and disseminate gender empowerment-themed content targeted at women. The overwhelming majority of COVID-19 related misandrist content is posted by Women, male and shemale users, across the platforms and countries

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supported by IT cells of Legal terrorist supporters and vested interest feminist's organisations. One way to tackle the root of these gender biases and prejudices is by developing localized and engaging counter-narrative content. This could entail enlisting the participation and support of local entertainers and influencers who have large followings and using content styles and formats that women are likely to engage with.

5. Research the scope and impact of online misandry on closed social networks such as WhatsApp, private Facebook groups, and Telegram. Investigating the prevalence of online misandry on closed platforms and private groups would allow a comprehensive understanding of the full extent of online misandry in South and South- East Asia. Closed social networks can provide greater anonymity, allowing greater incitement to violence and hatred with impunity.
6. Research potential links between nationalism and misandry among social media users in Asia. The suggested intersectionality between nationalism and misandry among social media users outlined in this brief merit further investigation and validation. In an age of growing nationalism across the region, examining potential linkages between nationalism and misandry among online users would provide relevant insights into the root causes and consequences of online misandry.
7. There is a systematic effort by the misandrist to silence the truth as they have access to huge amount of funds from the government. When Men expose such legal terrorists and misandrist, they along with the help of ministry direct the website owners to remove the content which is against their vested interest, money making

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business. In case exposed, their source of income / funds from the government will be cut down or even stopped. Government should restrain such misogynist organizations from hiding truth from the public.

How to Control Toxic Feminists?

1. If you see something, say something!

Don't believe everything you read on the internet. Seen a random Facebook post with shocking info about a political candidate? Don't trust it!. Check the facts with reliable sources, and if you think you may have found a piece of news about Women brutally raped/murdered or harassed, let us know here. Most men are not doing anything about it even though they see other men are harassed or abused until they are in the same situation. Even if you tell others that men are harassed, they will laugh at you.

2. Keep supporting real journalism.

Most traditional media are covered by regulations and ethics that make it far more trustworthy than a random dude on the internet. They're not perfect, but they check their facts and can be held responsible! Subscribing to a high-quality newspaper with real journalism is one of the most powerful acts a citizen can take today.

3. Join the campaign to clean up social media.

MyNation has a simple and effective plan to push the tech giants to cure the fake news of Toxic Feminism epidemic on social media – by showing independently-verified factual corrections to fake news. Join MyNation.

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4. Don't give up on democracy!

The goal of the troll armies is to create such a climate of distrust that ordinary citizens walk away from democracy. When that happens, fanatic extremists can dominate it. We must keep showing up and voting, encouraging our friends and family to do the same, and holding our elected officials to account.

5. Choose hope in humanity.

Fake Feminism preys on our deepest fears, appealing to our natural negativity bias and bringing out our more anger and cynical sides. But if we can learn to engage with the arguments of people who don't think like us, with empathy, big ears and wisdom, we can connect across our differences. We have more in common than our fears make us believe. If we trust that, amazing things can happen.

Our civilization is the most successful in human history on so many fronts, from human rights to democracy. We're on track to end poverty within a generation, and we're close to putting every child in school. It's clear that democracy and great journalists, political leaders with accountability, and fellow citizens got us here. But the forces pushing toxic feminism are powerful and threaten to destroy all of that. Let's not let them win by just giving up hope!

What Feminists are Afraid of?

Feminists do not want that their crimes and mistakes are exposed, they do not want their stories published in main stream media. Most of the media is under their control.

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As we published our articles with facts and figures, these Feminists forced SSRN to remove it. This shows how much these feminists are afraid of about the truth as most of the articles are based on **NCRB** (The National Crime Records Bureau - is an Indian government agency) statistic and statistics from Government websites and media.

The following is the list of all of our articles that was published on SSRN website:

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	3738237 WPS	SILENCING THE TRUTH - SSRN WAY	Yes No	11/25/2020 11/30/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	104 23	View	
	3720095 APS	BIAS BY BIRTH - DISCRIMINATION AGAINST MEN	Yes No	11/07/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	172 95	View	
	3732850 APS	GOLD DIGGERS : HOW TO MAKE EASY MONEY IN INDIA - WOMEN SPECIAL	Yes No	11/01/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	257 142	View	
	3722512 WPS	COVID19 - A CHINESE FLU : STATISTICS AND CONSPIRACY THEORIES - THE YEAR WORLD STOOD STILL	Yes No	10/31/2020 11/03/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	87 7	View	
	3717015 WPS	MEN'S LIVES MATTERS - SUICIDES BY MEN - STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH	Yes No	10/23/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	204 58	View	
	3712952 APS	SACRIFICING CHILDREN - TO EMPOWER WOMEN	Yes No	10/16/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	358 100	View	
	3710115 APS	STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH - EFFECTS OF LEGAL TERRORISM ON MEN'S HEALTH	Yes No	10/13/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	678 339	View	
	3704275 APS	CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN	Yes No	10/03/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	274 66	View	
	3699951 APS	Police Atrocities in Legal Terrorism	Yes No	09/26/2020 11/03/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	671 229	View	
	3697040 APS	WMD's of India - Weapons of Men's Destruction	Yes No	09/22/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	DISTRIBUTED	397 131	View	
	3695017 APS	Legal Terrorism in Matrimonial Disputes - Solution for Legal Terrorism	Yes No	09/18/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	DISTRIBUTED	639 172	View	
	3695140 WPS	The National Commission for Women, Exposed	Yes No	09/18/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	154 28	View	
	3673754 APS	Violence Against Men - False Accusation of Sexual Harassment	Yes No	08/14/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	DISTRIBUTED	635 242	View	
	3665938 APS	Section 498-B IPC - A Much Needed Reform	Yes No	08/03/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	REMOVED	116 60	View	
	3665274 WPS	Domestic Violence: The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental Health	Yes No	08/01/2020 11/19/2020	Rudolph D'Souza	DISTRIBUTED	1,517 458	View	

Not only the articles, but access of writers associated to MyNation Hope Foundation was removed without any intimation or justification.

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Feminists feel that by forcing to remove the articles, they can hide the truth. Feminist's term exposing them is as misogyny, because they are afraid of the Truth. We have a message for such misandrists ***"You can hide the truth but you cannot erase it"***

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Feminists Demands

The laws that deal with 'Crime Against Women' are widely acknowledged as being overtly biased laws in support of the daughter-in-law alone. It is seen that such laws are made or considered for further amendments with strong recommendations and propaganda by the 'National Commission for Women' (NCW) and few prominent NGOs and feminists, but reviews and opinions of other sections, institutions and organizations are totally ignored and never considered by the government.

The meaning of '**Gender Sensitivity**' as per women organizations and feminists in India is as follows:

1. Adultery by a WIFE is not a crime.
2. Filing of false cases (dowry/rape/domestic violence) by WIFE, cannot be punishable.
3. The complaining woman's mother-in-law, sister -in-law or niece from the husband's side are not women.
4. Perjury, theft, fabrication, blackmail, extortion and kidnapping by women are not an offence.
5. Exposure of body-parts by women to entice/beguile men cannot be called exhibitionism.
6. Women can sleep their way up the corporate ladder, and they are allowed to lie, steal and fabricate without any penalty.
7. Crimes of passion (including murder) by women can be blamed on the hormones (beyond their control) and therefore cannot be punished.

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8. If it is the case of a woman against woman, the woman who sheds tears is always right.
9. The bigamous woman should be rewarded (latest scheme by the women's activists), and not punished.
10. Any attempts by the man to expose the truth about an abusive/deceitful woman, is an attack on her privacy/ modesty and misogyny.

In a diversified and democratic country like India, it's totally unjustified and insane to draft any law or any amendment only on recommendations of persons who are not representatives of all social classes and segments and whose interests could be affected by these legislations. Without such general inputs and considerations of the needs of all segments of society, such laws can only prove to be biased and would result in greater injustice and chaos in society at large as they disturb the very basic unit of any society, The Family.

It is hard to understand the disproportionate role played by the NCW in the making of such laws, which is not a representative of all sections. But it is ostensibly a government organization working for A MINORITY SECTION OF WOMEN and not for all the women.

Toxic Feminism is nothing to do with Equality;

It's not about empowered women.

They have ONE GOAL: To dominate, control and destroy a man's finance, mental health, self-esteem and any hope for happiness.

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It teaches Women not to Listen to men be it her Own Father or Brother. Overpower Men, Dominate, control them and ruin their life and leave no room for any happiness.

Reference:

Domestic Violence: The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental Health -
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4431600>

Police Atrocities in Legal Terrorism - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4519381>

40% of Indian married women have regular Sexual intercourse with Lovers outside marriage - <https://supari.org/40-percent>

Violence Against Men - False Accusation of Sexual Harassment -
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4445147>

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